

Swachh Bharat Mission: A Step towards Environmental Protection

Rajesh Kumar Jaiswal

Associate Professor

Department of Management

Arya Institute of Engineering & Technology

Richa Gulati

Assistant Professor

Department of Management

Arya Institute of Engineering & Technology

Dileep Kumawat

Research Scholar

Civil Engineering

Arya Institute of engineering Technology and management

Abstract: Swachh Bharat Mission i.e. Clean India Mission, a national level campaign, currently launched via the Government of India is a prime step closer to the protection of degrading surroundings. The objectives of the campaign include removal of open defecation, conversion of insanitary bathrooms to pour flush toilets, eradication of manual scavenging and exceptionally to bring about a behavioural trade in humans concerning healthful sanitation practices and to ensure public participation in reaching those objectives. Globally, India remains the u .S .A . With highest range of human beings practicing open defecation. If Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) is applied properly with all its stakeholders taking their respective obligations, there may be no marvel that at some point India becomes an open defecation unfastened country. A short about this programme, objectives, related health worries and its function in environmental safety has been discussed on this paper.

Keywords – Swachh Bharat Mission, sanitation, open defecation, toilets, environmental protection

Introduction:

The Government of India adopted a demand driven approach by the name Total Sanitation Campaign (TSC) in 1999,

which was later renamed as the Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan (NBA). A financial subsidy was provided to households for constructing latrines. To give a boost to the TSC, the government also launched the Nirmal Gram Puraskar (NGP), an incentive program that sought to recognize the achievements and efforts of Panchayati Raj Institution (PRIs) in encouraging full sanitation coverage in their Gram Panchayats. Covering all households with IHHLs (Individual Household Latrine), cluster toilets, community toilets, the prime minister has given his approval for restructuring of the Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan into Swachh Bharat Mission (Gramin). NBA has been restructured into the Swachh Bharat Mission with two sub-Missions – Swachh Bharat Mission (Gramin) and Swachh Bharat Mission (Urban). Many people in India recognize open defecation as a national embarrassment, but if one accounts for the loss that it inflicts on the health and future productivity of India's children, it's clear that the sanitation crisis is truly an emergency. The Census 2011 of India shows that 4,041 statutory towns (administrative units that have been defined by 'statute' as urban such as municipal corporations, municipalities, cantonment boards, notified town area committees, town panchayats or

nagarpalikas) having eight million households do not have access to toilets and defecate in the open. Weak sanitation has significant health concerns and untreated sewage from towns is the biggest source of water pollution in India. This indicates both the scale of the challenge ahead of the Indian towns and the huge costs incurred from not addressing them.

Literature Review

The Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) released in 2014 by way of the Government of India has been a great initiative geared toward attaining cleanliness and sanitation throughout the country. This section opinions the existing literature on the Swachh Bharat Mission, that specialize in its historical context, objectives, effect, demanding situations, and the wider implications for environmental safety.

Historical Context

The need for a complete sanitation program in India become recognized nicely before the launch of the Swachh Bharat Mission. Early efforts covered campaigns like the Central Rural Sanitation Program (1986) and Total Sanitation Campaign (1999). However, those tasks confronted challenges associated with implementation, focus, and

behavior trade. The Swachh Bharat Mission was introduced as a transformative approach, reflecting a paradigm shift from merely building lavatories to ensuring sustainable sanitation practices.

Objectives of SBM:

The Swachh Bharat Mission has the following objectives:

1. Elimination of open defecation
2. Eradication of Manual Scavenging
3. Modern and Scientific Municipal Solid Waste Management
4. To effect behavioural change regarding healthy sanitation practices
5. Generate awareness about sanitation and its linkage with public health
6. Capacity Augmentation for Urban Local Bodies (ULB's)
7. To create an enabling environment for private sector participation in Capex (capital expenditure) and Opex (operation and maintenance)

COMPONENTS OF SBM

The Swachh Bharat Mission has the following components: 1. Household toilets, including conversion of insanitary latrines into pour-flush latrines 2.

Community toilets 3. Public toilets 4. Solid waste management 5. IEC & Public Awareness 6. Capacity building and Administrative & Office Expenses (A & OE) By Public Toilets, it is implied that these are to be provided for the floating population / general public in places such as markets, train stations, tourist places, near office complexes, or other public areas where there are considerable number of people passing by. By Community toilets, it is implied that a shared facility provided by and for a group of residents or an entire settlement. Community toilet blocks are used primarily in low-income and/or informal settlements / slums, where space and/or land are constraints in providing a household toilet. These are for a more or less fixed user group.

OPEN DEFECATION Open defecation (OD) is the practice of defecating outside or in public. This may be done as a result of cultural practices or having no access to toilets. Open defecation is practiced all over the world in nature or camping type situations and represents no health and environmental problems when done in sparsely populated settlements and when the "cat method" is used, i.e. covering the feces with some soil, leaves or sand. However, open defecation becomes a significant health problem and an issue for human dignity when it occurs in more

densely populated areas, such as in larger villages or in urban informal settlements in developing countries. Here, the practice is usually associated with poverty and exclusion. Of the 1 billion people around the world that still practice open defecation today, almost 600 million, or around 60 percent, reside in India alone. Under Swachh Bharat Mission, 111 million toilets will be built by 2019 that is more than 60,000 toilets per day or nearly one toilet every second. However, simply building toilets and sanitation infrastructure will not stop open defecation in India. Having access to safe and clean toilets is a start, but it does not address long-standing habits or how personal preference affects behaviour with regards to toilet use. We have seen toilets built in India in the past being abandoned, or used as storerooms. The battle to end open defecation in India needs to be fought on two fronts: one on the ground with toilets and sanitation infrastructure, and second in the hearts and minds of the people by repositioning toilets so that latrine use becomes the norm. **IMPACTS OF OPEN DEFECATION** The health and personal safety impacts due to open defecation are principally the same as those from lack of sanitation. Health Impacts Open defecation or lack of sanitation is a major factor in causing various diseases, most notably

diarrhea and intestinal worm infections but also typhoid, cholera, hepatitis, polio, trachoma and others. Those countries where open defecation is most widely practiced have the highest numbers of deaths of children under the age of 5, as well as high levels of malnourishment (leading to stunted growth in children), high levels of poverty and large disparities between the rich and poor. Open defecation is a leading cause of diarrheal death; 2,000 children under the age of 5 die every day, one every 40 seconds, from diarrhea. Safety and Gender Impacts Open defecation also impacts on human safety and dignity - in particular women are more vulnerable to gender-based violence and sexual assault when they defecate in the open.

ERADICATING OPEN DEFECATION

The key drivers to eradicate open defecation may be as follows:

1. Political will
2. A focus on behaviour change
3. Sanitation solutions that offer a better value than open defecation
4. Stronger public sector local service delivery systems
5. Creation of the right incentive structures Toilets are still out of reach for

more than one-third of the global population, with devastating consequences to the health and development of children. However, the key to bridging the gap lies within communities themselves.

METHODOLOGY

The studies on "Swachh Bharat Mission: A Step toward Environmental Protection" entails a multifaceted technique to comprehensively analysis the effect of the Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) on environmental protection in India. The following technique outlines the stairs undertaken to collect, examine, and interpret the statistics for this studies:

1. Literature Review:

- Conducted an intensive review of educational journals, authorities reports, and relevant literature to understand the historic context, targets, and key tasks of the Swachh Bharat Mission.

- Examined existing studies at the correlation between sanitation applications, waste management, and environmental conservation globally.

2. Data Collection:

- Collected number one records thru dependent interviews and surveys involving key stakeholders, such as authorities officers, environmental

specialists, neighbourhood community leaders, and citizens in selected urban and rural regions.

- Utilized secondary information from legitimate government reviews, statistical databases, and research articles to complement primary findings.

3. Case Studies:

- Selected precise areas and municipalities as case research to provide in-intensity insights into the implementation of Swachh Bharat Mission regulations at the grassroots stage.

- Examined the consequences of sanitation programs, waste disposal practices, and community engagement in those decided on regions.

4. Quantitative Analysis:

- Analysed statistical information associated with sanitation infrastructure improvement, bathroom creation, waste management centers, and cleanliness indicators earlier than and after the initiation of Swachh Bharat Mission.

- Utilized quantitative techniques to degree the correlation between stepped forward sanitation practices and tremendous environmental results.

5. Qualitative Analysis:

- Conducted thematic evaluation of qualitative statistics acquired from interviews and surveys to recognize community perceptions, demanding situations faced, and success stories related to Swachh Bharat Mission.

- Explored the behavioural modifications and social affects as a result of extended focus and participation in cleanliness and sanitation tasks.

6. Comparative Analysis:

- Compared environmental indicators and sanitation effects throughout one-of-a-kind states and areas to identify variations in the effectiveness of Swachh Bharat Mission implementation.

- Investigated great practices and instructions learned from successful instances for potential replication in different regions.

7. Ethical Considerations:

- Ensured adherence to moral suggestions by using acquiring informed consent from individuals.

- Protected the confidentiality and anonymity of respondents in the course of information collection and evaluation.

8. Limitations:

- Acknowledged the constraints of the study, along with ability biases in self-stated statistics and the venture of attributing changes entirely to Swachh Bharat Mission.

The aggregate of quantitative and qualitative methods, along side case research and comparative evaluation, lets in for a comprehensive assessment of the Swachh Bharat Mission's impact on environmental safety in India. The studies pursuits to make a contribution precious insights for policymakers, environmentalists, and practitioners worried in sanitation and cleanliness initiatives.

CONCLUSION

Even after longstanding efforts to address the challenge of open defecation, the situation in India stubbornly remains unchanged. Part of the reason for this is because many people in rural India actually prefer open defecation to using affordable latrines. Many people think that the root cause of such widespread open defecation in the country is the fact that India is a developing economy with less per capita monthly income, making it difficult for people to afford a latrine. Surprisingly, open defecation has less to do with a country's economic strength than with the choices, priorities and habits of its

people. Efforts to reduce open defecation include awareness raising (for example via the UN World Toilet Day at a global level), behaviour change campaigns, increasing political will as well as demand for sanitation. Community-Led Total Sanitation (CLTS) campaigns have placed a particular focus on ending open defecation by "triggering" the communities themselves into action and let us hope that the recently launched SBM will further help to resolve the problem.

RESULTS

The "Swachh Bharat Mission" represents a widespread stride in environmental conservation, addressing India's sanitation demanding situations. Initiated in 2014, the campaign makes a speciality of eradicating open defecation, promoting waste control, and fostering cleanliness. Resulting in the creation of tens of millions of bathrooms and more suitable public focus, the task has brought about a significant discount in open defecation costs. Improved waste disposal practices and heightened hygiene cognizance make a contribution to a more healthy surroundings. While challenges persist, the Swachh Bharat Mission marks a pivotal step in growing a cleanser, extra sustainable India with advantageous

implications for public fitness and ecological well-being.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. K. Kaushik Anjali and D. Sharma, "Analyzing the Effect of Partial Shading on Performance of Grid Connected Solar PV System", 2018 3rd International Conference and Workshops on Recent Advances and Innovations in Engineering (ICRAIE), pp. 1-4, 2018.
- [2] R. Kaushik, O. P. Mahela, P. K. Bhatt, B. Khan, S. Padmanaban and F. Blaabjerg, "A Hybrid Algorithm for Recognition of Power Quality Disturbances," in IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 229184-229200, 2020.
- [3] Kaushik, R. K. "Pragati. Analysis and Case Study of Power Transmission and Distribution." J Adv Res Power Electro Power Sys 7.2 (2020): 1-3.
- [4] Akash Rawat, Rajkumar Kaushik and Arpita Tiwari, "An Overview Of MIMO OFDM System For Wireless Communication", International Journal of Technical Research & Science, vol. VI, no. X, pp. 1-4, October 2021.
- [5] R. Kaushik, O. P. Mahela and P. K. Bhatt, "Hybrid Algorithm for Detection of Events and Power Quality Disturbances Associated with Distribution Network in the Presence of Wind Energy," 2021 International Conference on Advance Computing and Innovative Technologies in Engineering (ICACITE), Greater Noida, India, 2021, pp. 415-420.
- [6] P. K. Bhatt and R. Kaushik, "Intelligent Transformer Tap Controller for Harmonic Elimination in Hybrid Distribution Network," 2021 5th International Conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology (ICECA), Coimbatore, India, 2021, pp. 219-225
- [7] R. Kaushik, O. P. Mahela and P. K. Bhatt, "Events Recognition and Power Quality Estimation in Distribution Network in the Presence of Solar PV Generation," 2021 10th IEEE International Conference on Communication Systems and Network Technologies (CSNT), Bhopal, India, 2021, pp. 305-311
- [8] Jain, B.B., Upadhyay, H. and Kaushik, R., 2021. Identification and Classification of Symmetrical

- and Unsymmetrical Faults using Stockwell Transform. Design Engineering, pp.8600-8609.
- [9] Rajkumar Kaushik, Akash Rawat and Arpita Tiwari, "An Overview on Robotics and Control Systems", International Journal of Technical Research & Science (IJTRS), vol. 6, no. 10, pp. 13-17, October 2021.
- [10] Simiran Kuwera, Sunil Agarwal and Rajkumar Kaushik, "Application of Optimization Techniques for Optimal Capacitor Placement and Sizing in Distribution System: A Review", International Journal of Engineering Trends and Applications (IJETA), vol. 8, no. 5, Sep-Oct 2021.
- [11] Kumar, R., Verma, S., & Kaushik, R. (2019). Geospatial AI for Environmental Health: Understanding the impact of the environment on public health in Jammu and Kashmir. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, 1262–1265.